

1 **A supramolecular hybrid sensor based on cucurbit[8]uril, 2D-molibdenum**
2 **disulphide and diamond nanoparticles towards methyl viologen analysis**

3 Elías Blanco^a, Laura Rocha^a, María del Pozo^a, Luis Vázquez^b, María Dolores Petit-
4 Domínguez^a, Elena Casero^a, Carmen Quintana^{a*}

5 ^aDepartamento de Química Analítica y Análisis Instrumental. Facultad de Ciencias. c/
6 Francisco Tomás y Valiente, N°7. Campus de Excelencia de la Universidad Autónoma
7 de Madrid. 28049 Madrid. Spain.

8 ^bESISNA group, Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid (CSIC). c/ Sor Juana Inés
9 de la Cruz N°3. Campus de Excelencia de la Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. 28049
10 Madrid. Spain

11 *Corresponding author email: carmen.quintana@uam.es

12 **Abstract**

13 We develop an electrochemical sensor by using 2D-transition metal dichalcogenides
14 (TMD), specifically MoS₂, and nanoparticles stabilized with cucurbit[8]uril (CB[8])
15 incorporated together with them. Two different nanoparticles are assayed: diamond
16 nanoparticles (DNPs) and gold nanoparticles (AuNp). 0D materials, together with TMD,
17 provide increased conductivity and active surface while the macrocycle CB[8] affords
18 selectivity towards the guest methyl viologen (MV²⁺), also named paraquat. Glassy
19 Carbon (GC) electrodes are modified by drop-casting of suspensions of MoS₂, followed
20 by either a CB[8]-DNPs hybrid dispersion or a CB[8]-AuNp suspension. Atomic force
21 microscopy is employed for the morphological characterization of the electrochemical
22 sensor surface while cyclic voltammetry and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy
23 techniques allow the electrochemical characterization of the sensor. The well-established
24 signals of CB[8]-encapsulated MV²⁺ arise in voltammetric measurements when the
25 macrocycle modifies the 0D-materials. Once the sensor construction and differential

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26 pulse voltammetry parameters have been optimized for quantification purposes,
27 calibration procedures are performed with the platform GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs. This
28 sensing platform shows linear relations between peak intensity and the MV²⁺
29 concentration in the linear concentration range of (0.73 – 8.0) · 10⁻⁶ M with a limit of
30 detection of 2.2 · 10⁻⁷ M. Analyses of river water samples fortified with MV²⁺ at the μM
31 level shows recoveries of 100% with RSD values of 6.4 % (n = 3).

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33 **Keywords:** Molybdenum disulphide, diamond nanoparticles, cucurbit[8]uril, methyl
34 viologen, supramolecular chemistry.

35 36 **1. Introduction**

37 Chemical sensors based on supramolecular recognition incorporate, in the sensing layer,
38 a host that generates a measurable signal upon guest recognition. Although cyclodextrins
39 are still displaying their capabilities in sensor constructions, cucurbit[n]urils (CB[n]) have
40 emerged as a powerful alternative from the beginning of this century [1]. CB[n] are
41 pumpkin-shaped cyclic polymeric compounds composed of n (n= 5-10) glycoluryl units
42 and have two symmetrical portals delimited by carbonyl oxygen atoms, which allow
43 guests to be accommodated into the hydrophobic cavity [2]. The chemical nature of the
44 portals, the hydrophobic cavity and the host size are responsible of the CB[n] selectivity
45 to certain guests such as phenols, the amino acid tryptophan and the neurotransmitter
46 dopamine [3,4], among others.

47 Furthermore, 2D-, 1D- or 0D-nanoarchitectures made of different materials have been
48 functionalized with macrocycles, such as cyclodextrins and CB[n]s, for different
49 applications. In these hybrid systems, the nanomaterial provides properties like high
50 active surface, hardness, electric conductivity, or chemical stability while the host keeps

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the well-established supramolecular recognition capability exhibited in solution. In the literature, there are examples of macrocycle-modified carbon-based nanomaterials such as graphene and its oxide [5–7], nanotubes [8] and nanoparticles [9]. There are also examples of macrocycle-modified 1D-materials made of clays or gold [10]. Likewise, gold nanoparticles (AuNp) have been modified with macrocycles for the evaluation of CB[n] complexes dissociation constants [11], catalysis [12], synergistic chemophotothermal therapy for cancer [13] and chemical analysis [14,15].

In addition to these advances, two relatively new nanomaterials, namely 2D-transition metal dichalcogenides (TMD) and 0D-diamond nanoparticles (DNPs), are gaining attention due to their interesting properties and promising applications. TMD are materials characterized by an X-M-X (X = chalcogenide, M = metal) structure in each layer, with the TMD layers being weakly bonded between them by van der Waals forces. Therefore, their top-down synthesis approach from the bulk counterparts is easily performed by, for example, ultrasounds-mediated liquid phase exfoliation in appropriate solvents, such as mixtures of ethanol and water. Their large specific surface area and semiconducting character make them apposite to be included in electrochemical designs. Thus, the dichalcogenide MoS₂ has been applied for the oxygen reduction reaction [16] and the hydrogen evolution [17]. In addition, applications in nanophotonics and chemical sensing have been proposed [18, 19]. On the other hand, DNPs are commercially available and have a non-conducting core of sp³ carbon while the surface is composed of amorphous carbon with oxygen functionalities responsible of their electrocatalytic properties. They are non-toxic and can be used in fluorescence applications, polymer composites and as lubricants [20]. Compared with other carbon forms such as boron-doped diamond, DNPs are clearly an emerging nanomaterial in the electrochemical field where they have demonstrated their excellent properties [21,22].

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76 Viologen-containing molecules are guests of the macrocycles CB[7] and CB[8] and have
77 been successfully used in rotaxanes [23], biological [24] and sensing applications [25].
78 Methyl viologen (MV^{2+}) is a non-selective contact herbicide known as paraquat in
79 agricultural and toxicological fields and its efficiency and low cost have boosted its usage
80 despite its toxicity for organisms. In the human beings, it generates an inflammatory
81 response, harms different viscera such as heart, kidney and liver, as well as the neural
82 system, being also associated with the Parkinson disease [26–28]. Many countries have
83 banned it but it is still in use in more than 100 countries such as China, USA, Australia,
84 Japan, Argentina and Taiwan, even with an increased use [26, 29–31]. From the
85 environmental point of view, paraquat is highly resistant to microbial and chemical
86 degradation with a half-life higher than two years [26–28,32] and, because of its high
87 water solubility, its use can cause the pollution of water bodies and tap water [27,32,33].
88 Methods to analyse paraquat include: liquid chromatography [34], fluorescence [35],
89 chemiluminescence [36], chromogenic sprays for thin-layer chromatographic analysis
90 [37], immunochromatographic strips [27] and, also, electroanalysis [28,32,38–41].
91 Despite the recognition capability of CB[7] and CB[8] towards MV^{2+} and the need of
92 MV^{2+} chemical analysis because of its wide use and high toxicity, CB[n]-modified
93 electrochemical sensors facing MV^{2+} have been scarcely investigated in comparison with
94 analytical methodologies that include CB[n] for other analytes [5,25]. In addition, and in
95 the best of our knowledge, the modification of DNPs by CB[n]s has never been explored
96 and no work has studied the use of these macrocycles and 2D-TMD in the same device.
97 Therefore, this work proposes to develop an electrochemical sensor that takes the
98 advantages in sensitivity of the use of 2D-TMD and 0D-nanoparticles (i.e. AuNp and
99 DNPs) together with the selectivity derived from the molecular recognition properties of
100 CB[n] ($n = 7, 8$) that are anchored to the 0D-elements. Because MV^{2+} is a harmful and

101 still used herbicide, the analytical performance of this supramolecular platform will be
102 evaluated to determine MV^{2+} in river water samples.

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104 **2. Materials and methods**

105 **2.1. Reagents**

106 Molybdenum disulfide (MoS_2 , 90 nm powder), cucurbit[n]urils (CB[n], n = 7, 8), methyl
107 viologen dichloride hydrate ($MV^{2+} \cdot 2 Cl^- \cdot H_2O$), 5 nm-gold nanoparticles stabilized in
108 citrate buffer, hexaammineruthenium(II) chloride, 4,4'-oxydianiline (Oxy),
109 thiabendazole (Tbz) and carbendazim (Cbz) all 99% were obtained from Sigma Aldrich
110 (St. Louis, MO, USA). Diamond nanoparticles (DNPs) were obtained from SkySpring
111 Nanomaterials, Inc (Houston, Texas, USA). Phosphoric, acetic and boric acids, potassium
112 chloride, ethanol absolute (EtOH) and sodium hydroxide were purchased from Scharlab
113 (Senmanat, Spain). Sodium borohydride ($NaBH_4$) and tetrachloroauric(III) acid trihydrate
114 ($HAuCl_4 \cdot 3 H_2O$) were obtained from Riedel-de Haën (Seelze, Germany) and Across
115 Organics (Geel, Belgium), respectively. Nippon Gases España S.L.U. (Madrid, Spain)
116 supplied nitrogen gas. Ultrapure water was used and produced by a Milli-Q system
117 (trademark) of Merck Millipore (Billerica, Massachusetts, United States).

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119 **2.2. Instrumentation and materials**

120 An Autolab PGSTAT 302N employing GPES software (Metrohm Autolab, Utrecht,
121 Netherlands) equipped with a Frequency Response Analyzer (FRAII) from Eco-Chemie
122 (Utrecht, The Netherlands) was used for Cyclic and Differential Pulse Voltammetric (CV,
123 DPV) measurements and Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) experiments,
124 respectively. A glassy carbon (GC) electrode of 3 mm diameter was used as the working

125 electrode whilst the electrochemical cell was completed with a coiled platinum wire and
126 an Ag/AgCl/1 M KCl reference electrode.

127 The AFM measurements were made with a Nanoscope IIIa system (Veeco, USA) and
128 using silicon FESP cantilevers (Bruker, USA) with a nominal radius of curvature of 8 nm.
129 The topographical and phase-contrast images consisted of 512 x 512 pixels. Kelvin Force
130 Microscopy (KFM) and gradient capacitance (dC/dz) measurements were done with an
131 Agilent 5500 PicoPlus operating in the single pass mode. In these cases, Pt-coated tips
132 (ANSCM-PT from APPNano) with a nominal radius of curvature of 30 nm were used.
133 Note that in KFM, it is measured the contact potential difference (CPD) between the
134 cantilever tip and the sample. This signal is related to the sample work function [42].

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136 **2.3. Procedures**

137 *2.3.1. Synthesis of 2D- MoS₂*

138 A top-down solvent exfoliation strategy was used. Briefly, it consisted in first weighting
139 75 mg of MoS₂ and subsequently adding 10 mL of EtOH/water (45:55, v/v) [43].
140 Afterwards, the mixture was sonicated for 2 h in a bath, kept at 4 °C for one day, and then
141 centrifuged at 4000 rpm during 45 min. The resulting supernatant was collected and
142 maintained refrigerated while not in use. It is worth to note that we used solvents of non-
143 toxic greenness nature and, from a practical point of view, the low solvents vapour
144 pressure allowed drying the modified electrode at room temperature. As previously
145 reported, working in this way, suspensions of 0.130 mg/mL MoS₂ were obtained
146 according to ICP-MS measurements [22].

147 *2.3.2. Synthesis of CB[8]-AuNp*

148 CB[8]-stabilized gold nanoparticles (CB[8]-AuNp) were synthesized following a
149 previously reported procedure [12,44]. A HAuCl₄ aqueous solution (100 µL, 40 mM) was

150 added to 40 mL of EtOH/water (1:1 v/v) in an aqua regia-cleaned 100 mL round-bottom
151 flask and homogenised during few seconds to obtain a light-yellow solution.
152 Subsequently, a recently prepared aqueous solution of reductant NaBH₄ (100 μL, 0.1M)
153 was quickly added under energetic hand-swirling to generate the AuNp colloid. This
154 colloid was left undisturbed during one hour and a CB[8] aqueous solution was afterwards
155 added under agitation to achieve a 0.3 mM final concentration. The CB[8]-AuNp were
156 aged during 2 days before use.

157 *2.3.3. Synthesis of CB[8]-DNPs*

158 The purchased DNPs solid was first dispersed by sonication in water at a concentration
159 level of 1 mg/mL. Afterwards, a CB[8] quantity was accurately weighted in an eppendorf
160 tube and a defined DNPs dispersion volume was added to achieve a 0.3 mM CB[8] final
161 concentration. This mixture was afterwards subjected to bath sonication to obtain CB[8]-
162 DNPs.

163 *2.3.4. Electrochemical sensors preparation*

164 First, the bare GC was polished with alumina powder (0.3 μm), rinsed with ethanol and
165 water under sonication, and dried with N₂. Next, the modification was performed by
166 successive drop casting of 6 μL of 2D- MoS₂ and 6 μL of CB[8]-AuNp or CB[8]-DNPs
167 suspension, letting to dry at room temperature after each modification step.

168 *2.3.5. Atomic Force Microscopic measurements*

169 The topographical measurements were made in the dynamic mode. In all cases, the optical
170 microscope attached to the AFM was used to address the tip to zones where large
171 agglomerates were absent. Different zones were sampled. Likewise, different tips were
172 also used to discard artefacts due to the tip status. Also, several types of samples were
173 studied to be able to better identify the morphological features associated with the
174 different components of the sensor. A similar procedure was followed for the AFM

175 electrical measurements. These measurements were performed under nitrogen ambient to
176 avoid humidity effects. The analysis of the images was performed using the own software
177 of the equipment as well as with the free-software Gwyddion [45].

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179 *2.3.6. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) characterization*

180 EIS measurements were carried out in 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 7.0, employing $1.0 \cdot$
181 10^{-3} M MV^{2+} as a probe, and at the formal MV^{2+}/MV^{+} potential. The measurements were
182 performed in a frequency range of 0.1 Hz to 0.1 MHz with a sinusoidal voltage of 5 mV
183 amplitude. All potentials are reported with respect to an Ag/AgCl/1M KCl reference
184 electrode. Either the bare GC electrode or the modified ones (GC/MoS₂ or
185 GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs) were employed. The experimental data were presented in the
186 form of Nyquist plots.

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188 *2.3.7. Differential Pulse Voltammetry (DPV) measurements*

189 MV^{2+} electrochemical measurements were performed in oxygen-free solutions (using a
190 nitrogen flow) and with the DPV parameters of -0.9 V of initial potential, 60 mV of
191 amplitude, 0.5 s of interval time and 15 mV of potential step (scan rate of 30 mV/s), and
192 35 s of accumulation time.

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194 *2.3.8. Analysis of MV^{2+} in river water samples.*

195 River water samples were obtained from Zánacara River (Camino Dique Mol, Villar de
196 Cañas, Cuenca, Spain) and were kept refrigerated and protected from light until analysis.
197 An aliquot was fortified to $2.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M MV^{2+} , filtered through 0.45-micron nylon filter,

198 diluted 1:10 with 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 7 and, once deoxygenated, subjected to
199 analysis.

201 3. Results and discussion

202 In this work, it is evaluated the supramolecular recognition capability of CB[8], when the
203 host is anchored to 0D-materials and forming, together with 2D-MoS₂, an hybrid system.
204 Scheme 1 summarizes the sensor components and platform construction. The 2D-MoS₂
205 was first obtained by simple liquid phase exfoliation in EtOH:H₂O mediated by
206 ultrasounds (Scheme 1a). The 0D-nanomaterials, used along this work, were subjected to
207 CB[n] modification as described in sections 2.3.2 and 2.3.3. The configuration of the as-
208 synthesized suspensions, depicted in Scheme 1b where the CB[n] pumpkin-shaped
209 molecular structure is also shown, are assumed from previous works in literature [5, 6,
210 12,13,44]. Glassy carbon electrodes were first modified with the 2D-MoS₂ and then with
211 the CB[n]-0D systems as seen in Scheme 1c, constructions that were used to tackle the
212 MV²⁺ analysis by voltammetric measurements.

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214 **Scheme 1.** Overview of this work with sensor components and platform construction. (a)
 215 2D-MoS₂ production by a top-down method. (b) 0D-systems modification by CB[n]. (c)
 216 Modification of GC electrode: GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-AuNp and GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs
 217 sensors construction.

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 219 To properly demonstrate the capabilities of our sensor design, it is important to record the
 220 response towards MV²⁺ with sensors made of each individual nanomaterial employed to
 221 assess the need of their combined use as well as the contribution of each separate
 222 component on the final response of the dispositive towards the analyte. The
 223 electrochemical response of MV²⁺ on a GC electrode, either as free analyte or as guest
 224 into the CB[7] and CB[8] cavities, is well documented [5,46]. Redox reactions of non-
 225 complexed MV²⁺ and CB[8]-MV²⁺ complex are depicted in scheme 2.

227 **a** **b**
 228 Scheme 2. Redox reactions of non-complexed MV²⁺ (a) and CB[8]-MV²⁺ complex (b).
 229 Symbols (■, ▼, □, ▽) correspond to specific waves in Figures 1 and 2.

230 As shown in Figure 1A-D, the CV response of MV²⁺ in an unmodified GC (curves a of
 231 each figure, dashed lines) exhibits the expected behaviour described in the literature with
 232 waves ascribed to the non-complexed analyte for the MV²⁺/MV^{•+} reaction at -0.73 and -
 233 0.66 V for the reduction and oxidation, respectively (see also Scheme 2a highlighted with
 234 filled squares). The waves at more negative potentials (-1.06 and -1.00 V, featured with
 235 filled triangles) are ascribed to MV^{•+}/MV⁰ system. The adsorptive process associated to

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236 MV^0 previously described [47] is here clearly observed from the feature of the oxidation
237 signal at -1.00 V. Likewise, and according to the literature [5,48,49], the GC-CB[8]
238 electrode (Figure 1A, voltammogram b), discloses new waves due to MV^{2+} species hosted
239 by CB[8] (unfilled squares and triangles also seen in Scheme 2b). The waves due to non-
240 complexed MV^{2+} species display a much lower intensity than with just the bare electrode.
241 It is worth noting that the CB[8]-accommodated MV^{2+}/MV^{+} reactions (unfilled squares)
242 take place at less negative potential values (-0.54 and -0.48 V) than in the free guest case
243 (-0.73 and -0.66 V), which is an advantage in terms of selectivity from an electroanalytical
244 perspective. Therefore, this redox pair corresponding to the supramolecular complex will
245 be followed for paraquat analysis. On the contrary, MV^{+}/MV^0 reactions arise at -1.35
246 and -1.11 V (unfilled triangles), that is at more negative potential values than those
247 observed for the non-complexed analyte. Moreover, the inclusion complex formation
248 inhibits the adsorption of MV^0 on the electrode as can be concluded from the decrease of
249 the oxidation wave at -1.00 V.

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250 The 2D-MoS₂, a well-known nanomaterial with a high surface and semiconducting
251 character, also can prevent the MV^0 adsorption on the electrode, as shown in
252 voltammogram b of Figure 1B, in contrast to the observed MV^{+}/MV^0 pair obtained for
253 the bare GC (voltammogram a). Furthermore, the GC/MoS₂ response did not show
254 noticeable peak potential shifts or relevant influence on the peak intensities related to the
255 MV^{2+}/MV^{+} redox pair. In contrast, intensity improvements of the MV^{2+}/MV^{+} waves
256 are obtained with the use of DNPs because of their electrocatalysis and large surface
257 contribution (Figure 1C, voltammogram b) [21,43]. It is also noticed that the CB[8]
258 molecular recognition properties remain unaffected when this species is in the hybrid
259 form CB[8]-DNPs (Figure 1C, voltammogram c). A similar conclusion can be extracted
260 from the use of AuNp stabilized with CB[8] depicted in Figure 1D (voltammogram c). In

261 this figure, the response of a GC modified with commercial AuNp stabilized with citrate
 262 (voltammogram b) is also included for comparison. In this later case, no improvement in
 263 any of the electrochemical signals can be observed.

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265 **Figure 1.** Cyclic voltammograms of 1.0 mM MV^{2+} recorded in 0.1 M phosphate buffer
 266 pH 7 at 100 mV/s with a bare GC electrode (curve a, black dashed lines) and electrodes
 267 modified with the different nanomaterials under investigation. (A) Effect of CB[8] on the
 268 MV^{2+} response (curve b) studied with the sensor GC/CB[8]. (B) Effect of MoS_2 on the
 269 MV^{2+} response (curve b) with the GC/ MoS_2 electrode. (C) Effect of DNPs on MV^{2+}
 270 response, either unmodified (curve b, GC/DNPs) or modified with CB[8] (curve c,
 271 GC/CB[8]-DNPs). (D) Effect of AuNp on MV^{2+} response, either (curve b, GC/AuNp
 272 commercial), and of CB[8]-modified AuNp (curve c, GC/CB[8]-AuNp).

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274 From these experiments, it is evident that the CB[8] capability of MV^{2+} recognition is
 275 preserved when the chemical receptor modifies the OD-materials AuNp and DNPs.

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276 Encouraged with these results, we evaluated the performance of hybrids containing the
277 2D-TMD and the 0D-nanomaterials stabilized with the receptor.

278 We have previously demonstrated the synergistic effect existing between TMD
279 nanosheets and DNPs towards different electrooxidation processes [22,43,50], like other
280 authors have done with gold nanoparticles [51]. However, the selectivity of these
281 electroanalytical procedures could be improved in order to expand their field of
282 application to more areas including supramolecular recognition. In this sense, we try to
283 contribute to this goal by using CB[n] to achieve an extra selectivity. Therefore, hybrids
284 of MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs and MoS₂/CB[8]-AuNp were employed for the GC electrodes
285 modification. In addition, the same hybrids with CB[7] were studied to know which
286 macrocycle shows the best analytical response since both form supramolecular complexes
287 with MV²⁺, but with different stoichiometry.

288 As observed in Figure S1, there are no benefits in selectivity by using CB[7] in the hybrid
289 system. Although the electrochemical response of the GC/MoS₂/CB[7]-AuNp sensor
290 shows increases in currents for all signals, it is not possible to identify that one of
291 analytical interest corresponding to the supramolecular complex. Similar results were
292 obtained with a GC/MoS₂/CB[7]-DNPs sensor (data not shown). Therefore, the CB[7]
293 homologue was not employed for further investigations, and, in the next step, the response
294 of the whole sensor containing CB[8] is discussed.

295 As shown in the cyclic voltammograms depicted in Figures 2A and 2B, the
296 electroanalytical signal of the pair of interest, corresponding to the supramolecular
297 complex, is really increased because of the synergistic effect between the nanomaterials
298 employed. The response is clearly higher for the MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs combination as it is
299 depicted in Figure 2C that shows the comparison between both systems.

Figure 2. Cyclic voltammograms of 1.0 mM MV^{2+} in 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 7 at 100 mV/s. (A) (a) GC/CB[8]-DNPs and (b) GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs. (B) (a) GC/CB[8]-

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305 AuNp and (b) GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-AuNp. C) (a) GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs and (b)
306 GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-AuNp.

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308 The synergistic effect of the combination of the three materials is demonstrated by
309 comparing the response of the GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs sensor (Figure 2C curve b) with
310 that of sensors containing just MoS₂ (Figure 1B, curve b) and CB[8]-DNPs (Figure 2A,
311 curve a). The most remarkable characteristics are that the peaks of MV²⁺/MV⁺ species
312 inside CB[8] cavity are clearly seen in addition to the peak current increase produced
313 from the nanomaterials combination. This collaborative effect could be due to the certain
314 affinity that CB[8], and to a less extent DNPs, shows to adsorb on the large MoS₂ flake
315 surface as AFM data shows (see below). Thus, more CB[8] molecules on MoS₂ flakes
316 are exposed to MV²⁺ molecules.

317 As a result of all these experiments, and because of the higher intensities obtained when
318 DNPs were used with respect to AuNp, we chose the carbon-based 0D-material for further
319 experimentation related to both: the characterization of the sensor surface (through the
320 evaluation of the electroactive area, AFM and EIS experiments), and the optimization of
321 an analytical method towards MV²⁺ analysis.

322 The electrochemical surface area was determined, with the bare and the different modified
323 electrodes, in a 1M KCl solution containing 10 mM [Ru(NH₃)₆]^{2+/3+} as redox probe as its
324 electron transfer does not depend on an interaction with a functional group or surface
325 place [52]. The measured peak current (I_p) is related with the electrochemical surface area
326 (A) through the Randles-Sevick equation:

$$327 \quad I_p = (2.69 \times 10^5) n^{3/2} A D^{1/2} v^{1/2} C \text{ (equation 1)}$$

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328 where v is the scan rate, n the number of electrons, D the diffusion coefficient ($9.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$
329 $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{2+/3+}$ at 22°C [53]) and C the concentration of the redox compound.
330 From the slope of the corresponding $I_{\text{pa}} \text{ vs } v^{1/2}$ plots, electroactive surface areas of (0.070
331 ± 0.008) cm^2 and (0.149 ± 0.009) cm^2 were obtained for the bare GC and the
332 GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs electrodes, respectively. These values confirm that the presence
333 of both nanomaterials results in a considerable increase of the effective area.
334 The redox couple $\text{MV}^{2+}/\text{MV}^{+}$ encapsulated inside CB[8] showed an analytical interesting
335 displacement to less negative potentials making this system less likely to suffer from
336 potential interferences. Accordingly, the electrochemical oxidation of this pair was the one
337 monitored for the paraquat analysis. Consequently, the scanned potential window was
338 shortened for the optimization of the analytical methodology.

3.1. Sensor construction optimization

341 We optimized the MoS₂ concentration employed in the first layer by using the non-diluted
342 suspension and the ones obtained by dilution in EtOH:H₂O. A cyclic voltammetry scan
343 of MV^{2+} solution was performed with each resulting sensor and the corresponding results
344 are shown in Figure S2A. Since the undiluted TMD suspension (curve b) showed the
345 largest response in comparison with those obtained with the 1:5 and 1:10 dilutions (c and
346 d, respectively), it was chosen for further experimentation. In addition, Figure S2A
347 evinces the above explained MoS₂ effect on the signals enhancement of the MV^{2+} -CB[8]
348 complex with respect to the uncomplexed MV^{2+} waves (curve a).

349 In addition, we optimized the CB[8] amount for the sensor GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs
350 construction to attain the maximum MV^{2+} -CB[8] complex on the surface.
351 Experimentally, three CB[8] concentrations were assayed in the DNPs dispersion. Each
352 aqueous CB[8]-DNPs dispersion was afterwards deposited on a GC/MoS₂ electrode and

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353 subjected to CV analysis. The corresponding results are depicted in Figure S2B. It is seen
354 that the larger the CB[8] concentration, the lower the signals due to free MV²⁺ species,
355 and the higher the CB[8]-MV²⁺ intensities. However, it should be noted that the 0.6 mM
356 suspension homogeneity was poorer than the 0.3 mM one, which could result in lower
357 signals reproducibility. Therefore, 0.3 mM was chosen as optimal for the DNPs
358 modification.

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360 ***3.2. AFM and EIS characterization***

361 The sensor surface was characterized by both, AFM and EIS techniques. Figure 3 shows
362 the characteristic AFM data obtained on the Si/MoS₂ sample. In Figure 3A, a large, 12 x
363 12 μm², AFM micrograph is displayed, where large flakes or platelets corresponding to
364 MoS₂ flakes are clearly visible. In Figure 3B, the surface profile across a single flake,
365 indicated by the solid line drawn in the AFM image, is shown. The thickness of this flake
366 is close to 4 nm. A certain roughness is observed on top of the flake. In fact, when the
367 rms roughness of the flakes of the AFM image is analysed, a value of 1.8 nm is obtained.
368 This fact can be due to the deposition of tiny structures produced by the preparation
369 method that are observed in the inset of the Figure 3A that shows, with a greater detail,
370 the surface of one of these flakes.

371

372 **Figure 3.** (A) 12 x 12 μm^2 AFM topographical image of the Si/MoS₂ sample. Inset: 1.7
 373 x 1.7 μm^2 AFM image of a MoS₂ flake; (B) Surface profile along the solid line depicted
 374 in the top image.

375

376 In Figure 4A, it is shown a three-dimensional view of a typical AFM image obtained for
 377 the Si/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs sample. Large and rough aggregates of DNPs are formed
 378 (notice the large vertical scale). This kind of aggregation of the DNPs particles is well
 379 known [43, 54]. We have chosen this sort of 3D representation with illumination in order
 380 to evince the thin flakes existing on the surface around the large agglomerates. The top-
 381 view image in Figure 4B corresponds to one AFM image taken on one of these flat areas.
 382 Here, the flakes structures are clearly observed. In addition, dot structures with different
 383 sizes are found scattered on the surface as well as on the flakes. The surface profile along
 384 one of the flakes (solid line) is shown in Figure 4E. Now, the flake thickness is close to 6
 385 nm, larger than that of the MoS₂ flakes. Moreover, the flake surface is not as smooth as

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386 that of the MoS₂ flakes. This is better appreciated in the three dimensional view of this
387 flake displayed in Figure 4F. The whole flake surface shows some sort of corrugation,
388 visually different from that observed for the bare MoS₂ flakes (inset of Figure 3A). This
389 corrugation likely comes from CB[8] deposits since its height relative to the flake
390 thickness is always clearly smaller than the average DNPs diameter of 10 nm. Moreover,
391 the thickness of this CB[8] deposit is not constant since, for instance, the bottom part of
392 the flake in Figure 4F (see also Figure 4E) is smoother and thinner than the rest of the
393 flake surface. This fact suggests an uneven CB[8] aggregation on top of the flakes. These
394 differences lead to quite different roughness values for both types of flakes. Thus, whereas
395 the MoS₂ flakes have rms roughness of 1.8 nm, those of the MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs sample
396 have a value close to 6 nm. This difference is also seen in the plots of the height
397 distributions of the images (Figure 4G). Both plots display a large peak centred at zero
398 that corresponds to the substrate areas and a second peak, located at higher x-axis values,
399 which corresponds to the flake surface (note that the x-axis represents the pixel height in
400 the image). Clearly, for the MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs sample this second peak appears at larger
401 heights (i.e., flake thickness), and also is considerably broader, than the corresponding
402 peak for the bare MoS₂ structures.

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403 In addition to this corrugation, clear dot structures, mainly localized at the perimeter of
404 the flake, are seen in Figure 4F. These well-defined structures, with heights ranging from
405 8 to 15 nm, should correspond to DNPs. They are also visible in the large top view image
406 (Figure 4B) as the brighter dot structures. They can be found on the flakes as well as on
407 the substrate surface. Their presence on the flake surface also contribute to the long tail
408 of the second peak of the height distribution for the MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs sample.

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409 A detailed inspection of the imaged dot structures surrounding the flakes reveals that there
410 are dots of different heights (note that the dot height is not affected by the broader

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411 dimension of the KFM tip). Figure 4H shows the height distribution of these
412 nanostructures. Clearly, there are two peaks, one for the nanostructures with 1-4 nm and
413 other one, broader, for heights in the 10-16 nm. The first one should be related to CB[8]
414 deposits whereas the last one is related to single or aggregated DNPs. This assignment is
415 supported by the KFM and dC/dz images (Figures 4C and D, respectively) taken
416 simultaneously to Figure 4B. The KFM image only shows contrast, with respect to the
417 substrate, at the flakes. In these last structures the CPD is around 0.13 V higher than in
418 the surrounding areas. A close inspection shows that this contrast comes mainly from the
419 thicker zones of the flakes. Note that, in this case, the isolated dots do not yield any
420 contrast. In contrast, Figure 4D shows a dark contrast at the whole flake surface.
421 Furthermore, a darker, although subtle, contrast is found on the dot structures displaying
422 larger heights, i.e. those associated to DNPs, whereas the tiny ones, related to CB[8]
423 isolated deposits do not display any contrast with respect to the substrate. It is not
424 surprising that the imaged structures show different contrast in these two AFM modes
425 since they sample different physical properties. Thus, KFM samples the surface potential
426 whereas the dC/dz signal depends on the local dielectric constant [42]. Finally, it is worth
427 to note that whereas the CB[8] deposits on the substrate are rather small, localized, and
428 isolated, those on top of the flakes are larger in size and more continuous. These data
429 imply that CB[8] presents some sort of affinity for the MoS₂ surface.

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432 **Figure 4** (A) $1.2 \times 1.2 \mu\text{m}^2$ 3D AFM topographical image of the Si/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs

433 sample. The three-dimensional view is illuminated in order to highlight the MoS₂ flakes

434 on the substrate; (B) $3.5 \times 3.5 \mu\text{m}^2$ top view AFM image taken on a large flake area similar

435 to that indicated by the solid arrow; (C) Corresponding KFM image; (D) Corresponding

436 dC/dz image; (E) Surface profile along the solid line depicted in (B). (F) 1 x 1.1 μm^2 3D
 437 AFM image of the flake indicated by the dashed arrow; (G) Height distributions for the
 438 AFM images shown in Figure 3A (MoS_2 , dashed line) and (B) ($\text{MoS}_2/\text{CB}[8]\text{-DNPs}$, solid
 439 line); (H) Distribution of the maximum height of the scattered dot structures surrounding
 440 the flakes in (B).

441
 442 In addition to the AFM morphological characterization, EIS experiments were performed
 443 for the characterization of each step of the sensor construction (Figure 5). From the
 444 results, we found that the greatest influence of each layer was not in the charge transfer
 445 process but rather in the mass-transfer process. The Nyquist plot for the bare GC electrode
 446 corresponds to a fast electrochemical process. The recorded slope (slope ≈ 1) in the region
 447 of the low frequencies suggests that semi-infinite linear diffusion rules the mass-transfer
 448 process [55]. However, when the modified electrodes are investigated, slopes higher than
 449 1, related to adsorption processes (1.4 and 1.7 for GC/ MoS_2 and GC/ $\text{MoS}_2/\text{CB}[8]\text{-DNPs}$,
 450 respectively) are observed [56].

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452 **Figure 5.** Nyquist plots of 1.0 mM MV^{2+} solutions in phosphate buffer 0.1 M at the formal
453 potential of the redox pair, in the 0.1 Hz to 0.1 MHz frequency range. Sinusoidal voltage
454 of 5 mV amplitude.

455 **3.3. Instrumental variables optimization**

456 Differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) offers a greater sensitivity than CV, which is
457 required for analytical purposes. Accordingly, we moved to DPV, being the parameters
458 of amplitude, scan rate (studied by means of both interval time and potential step) firstly
459 scrutinized. An amplitude range of 10 to 100 mV in steps of 10 mV was assayed. The
460 best result was obtained for 60 mV in a compromise between sensitivity and selectivity
461 because, the higher the amplitude, the greater the current intensity but also the broader
462 the peak.

463 Next, we optimized the scan rate through the individual variation of the interval time and
464 the potential step. The best results, in terms of the peak current, are obtained for an
465 interval time and a potential step of 0.5 s and 15 mV, respectively. These conditions lead
466 to a scan rate of 30 mV/s.

467 Moreover, we tested the effect of the accumulation time at the initial potential (-0.9 V) in
468 the analytical signal. This variable was explored at three MV^{2+} levels, specifically 2.5,
469 5.0 and 7.5 μM , and the results are presented in Figure S3. We found that the higher the
470 accumulation time, the greater the recorded peak intensity with larger currents for higher
471 concentrations. At the concentration of 7.5×10^{-6} M an increased intensity was observed
472 during the first 20 seconds. This was not the case at 5.0×10^{-6} M where the
473 GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs surface was saturated for times longer than 25 s. At 2.5×10^{-6} M
474 a similar behaviour was observed but now the plateau was reached at 35 s. Therefore, this
475 value was chosen as the optimum to be capable of achieving the MV^{2+} quantification at
476 low concentration levels.

477 **3.4. Influence of the MV^{2+} concentration in the peak current. Analytical data.**

478 Once the sensor construction and the experimental variables were optimized, we studied
479 the influence of the MV^{2+} concentration in the peak current. The corresponding results
480 are depicted in Figure 6.

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483 **Figure 6.** DPV calibration graph of MV^{2+} with GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs in 0.1 M
484 phosphate buffer pH 7. Accumulation time = 35 s, $E_{ac} = -0.9$ V, amplitude = 60 mV, scan
485 rate = 30 mV/s.

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487 The voltammograms in the inset show the signals of supporting electrolyte (black line)
488 and for $1.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ to $8.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M MV^{2+} where it is seen that the higher the analyte
489 concentration, the greater the intensity of the peak corresponding to the supramolecular
490 complex. The corresponding calibration plot shows averaged peak currents and standard
491 deviations ($n=3$) for each assayed concentration. Signals and concentrations were linearly
492 correlated by the equation I_p (A) = $(0.73 \pm 0.01) [MV^{2+}]$ (M) + $(0.72 \pm 0.05) \cdot 10^{-6}$ with

493 $R^2 = 0.998$ in the concentration range of $(0.73 - 8.0) \times 10^{-6}$ M. For all the concentration
 494 levels inspected, the relative standard deviations (n=3) were lower than 11% and 3.6%
 495 for different sensors and in terms of repeatability in successive cycles, respectively. The
 496 good fit between the experimental data and the fitted equation is demonstrated by Er
 497 values lower than 3.0%. The limit of detection (LD) and the limit of quantification (LQ)
 498 were calculated from the standard deviation of blank solution data and $2.2 \cdot 10^{-7}$ M and
 499 $7.3 \cdot 10^{-7}$ M were found, respectively. This limit of quantification is below the Drinking
 500 Water Equivalent Level (DWEL) of the United States Environmental Protection Agency
 501 for paraquat [57]. For comparative purposes, Table 1 summarizes the analytical properties
 502 of several sensors for MV^{2+} analysis found in the literature. The detection limit values
 503 herein included are similar to [39], or even better than [38], those reported with different
 504 electrochemical sensors. Although other methods [28,32] report lower detection limits
 505 with similar linear ranges for quantification purposes, it is worth noting that they lack the
 506 selectivity improvement derived from the CB[8] molecular recognition properties.

507 **Table 1.** Comparative analytical data of electrochemical sensors for MV^{2+} analysis

Sensing surface	LD (μM)	Linear range (μM)	Reference
(BiFE)/Cu	0.093	0.66 - 48	[28]
HAP-CPE	0.015	0.8 - 20	[32]
DNA/AuNp/Au	1.3	5.6 - 1000	[38]
(Cu ₂ O/PVP-GNs/GC-RDE)	0.27	1 - 200	[39]
Au ultramicroelectrode	0.12	1 - 10	[40]
PHTH-based PY GE	0.1	0.5 - 29.1	[41]
GC/MoS ₂ /CB[8]-DNPs	0.22	0.73 - 8.0	This work

508 (BiFE)/Cu: ex situ bismuth-film electrode. HAP-CPE: hydroxyapatite-modified carbon
 509 paste electrode. DNA/AuNp/Au: DNA/gold nanoparticles modified gold electrode.
 510 Cu₂O/PVP-GNs/GC-RDE: Cu₂O/polyvinyl pyrrolidone-graphene modified glassy
 511 carbon-rotating disk electrode. PHTH-based PY GE: Phthalocyanine-based pyrolytic
 512 graphite electrode

513 **3.5. Interference studies**

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3 514 It has been previously demonstrated that the use of CB[8] allows to eliminate the
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5 515 interference of: i) analytes negatively charged, ii) analytes that do not fit with the cavity
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7 516 size, iii) substances that could be detected at more negative potentials than -0.54 V
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10 517 because of having included CB8 in the sensor design. To evaluate the selectivity of our
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12 518 sensor, we tested different possible interference compounds that could be present together
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14 519 with MV^{2+} in aqueous samples: the fungicides thiabendazole (Tbz) and carbendazim
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16 520 (Cbz), and the aromatic diamine 4,4'-oxydianiline (Oxy). The experiments were
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19 521 performed as follows: solutions containing MV^{2+} at a concentration level of $8.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M
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21 522 MV^{2+} were measured alone and mixed with increasing concentrations of the
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24 523 corresponding interference. It was considered that a compound causes interference at a
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26 524 concentration level that produces a variation of 10 % in the initial MV^{2+} intensity current.
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29 525 From the obtained results, no interference was found for any of the fungicides up to 1:1
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31 526 concentration ratio respect to MV^{2+} . Moreover, increasing concentrations of Oxy did not
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34 527 produce interference up to $4.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M, which represents a 5-fold concentration level
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36 528 respect to MV^{2+} .

39 529 **3.6. Analytical application**

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42 530 MV^{2+} presents a high water solubility and its half-life in the environment is relatively
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44 531 large. Therefore, the performance of the developed GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs sensor was
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46 532 tested towards the MV^{2+} analysis in river water samples from Záncara river (Spain). To
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49 533 this end, river water aliquots of 1.0 mL, unfortified and fortified at different MV^{2+}
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51 534 concentrations, were diluted to 10.0 mL, with 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 7 employed as
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54 535 electrolyte. Although the DPV response recorded from the fortified solutions showed a
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56 536 linear increase of the current with increasing MV^{2+} amounts, no MV^{2+} was detected in
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59 537 the unfortified sample. Therefore, an aliquot of the river water was fortified at a $2.0 \cdot 10^{-$

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538 ⁵ M level, just subjected to a filtration pretreatment, diluted 1:10 with the electrolyte and
539 subjected to DPV analysis by the standard addition procedure. Figure S4 shows the
540 voltammograms recorded in this complex sample matrix where the MV²⁺ signal (red line)
541 is clearly observed with respect to the electrolyte. Figure S4 also shows the averaged peak
542 currents of the MV²⁺ standard additions in the $1.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ to $5.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M range. The peak
543 current fitted linearly with the analyte added according to the equation: $I_p (A) = (1.0 \pm$
544 $0.1) [MV^{2+}] (M) + (2.1 \pm 0.2) \cdot 10^{-6}$ with $r = 0.990$ ($n=3$). Data analysis was afterwards
545 made to assess whether the standard addition method was necessary or a simpler
546 interpolation in the external calibration equation could be used. We found significant
547 differences between the slopes of both calibration procedures, namely (0.73 ± 0.01) by
548 the external calibration procedure and (1.0 ± 0.1) by the standard addition methodology,
549 as the calculated t value was 4.9 while the tabulated t (95%) value was 2.8. These results
550 led us to conclude that matrix interference is produced and, consequently, standard
551 addition is required for MV²⁺ quantification. A concentration of $(2.0 \pm 0.1) \cdot 10^{-5}$ M was
552 found which means a good 100% of recovery with an enough precision (6.4 % RSD)
553 calculated from three different analyses.

554

555 **4. Conclusions**

556 We present the combination of materials with different dimensionality in the design of an
557 electrochemical sensor, namely GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs. The sensor design combines the
558 benefits in sensitivity derived from the use of MoS₂ nanosheets and diamond
559 nanoparticles together with the selectivity derived from the molecular recognition
560 properties of CB[8], which are evidenced towards the determination of the pesticide
561 paraquat. In addition, we have demonstrated that the molecular receptor CB[8] retains its
562 recognition properties when functionalising either gold or diamond nanoparticles. AFM

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563 characterization shows and enhanced adsorption on the MoS₂ flake surface of CB[8] and
564 to a less extent of DNPs. In addition, KFM measurements allow to distinguish between
565 CB[8] and DNP deposits. In the best of our knowledge, neither CB[n]-modified DNPs
566 nor the use of these macrocycles and 2D-TMD in the same device had ever been explored
567 before. Comparing both functionalized nanoparticles, AuNp and DNPs, the excellent
568 electrocatalytic properties of diamond ones, make the combination CB[8]-DNPs a
569 promising functionalized material for different electroanalytical applications.

570 The sensor responds linearly to MV²⁺ from 0.73 · 10⁻⁶ to 8.0 · 10⁻⁶ M with a LD of 2.2 ·
571 10⁻⁷ M. Moreover, the sensor capability to determine MV²⁺ in real river samples has been
572 proved with excellent recoveries for fortified samples at the μM level.

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Supplementary Information

A supramolecular hybrid sensor based on cucurbit[8]uril, 2D-molibdenum disulphide and diamond nanoparticles towards methyl viologen analysis.

Elías Blanco^a, Laura Rocha^a, María del Pozo^a, Luis Vázquez^b, María Dolores Petit-Domínguez^a, Elena Casero^a, Carmen Quintana^{a*}

^aDepartamento de Química Analítica y Análisis Instrumental. Facultad de Ciencias. c/ Francisco Tomás y Valiente, N°7. Campus de Excelencia de la Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. 28049 Madrid. Spain.

^bESISNA group, Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid (CSIC). c/ Sor Juana Inés de la Cruz N°3. Campus de Excelencia de la Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. 28049 Madrid. Spain

*Corresponding author email: carmen.quintana@uam.es

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21 **Figure S1.** Cyclic voltammograms of 1.0 mM MV²⁺ recorded in 0.1 M phosphate buffer

22 pH 7 at 100 mV/s. (a) Bare GC, (b) GC/MoS₂/CB[7]-AuNp.

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31 **Figure. S2.** Cyclic voltammograms of 1.0 mM MV^{2+} in 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 7 at
 32 100 mV/s recorded with the GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs sensor. (A) Effect of the dilution of
 33 MoS₂ suspension: Bare GC (a) undiluted MoS₂ (b), diluted 1:5 (c) and diluted 1:10 (d).
 34 Sensor with 0.3 mM CB[8] concentration for the synthesis of CB[8]-DNPs. (B) Effect of
 35 the CB[8] concentration: Bare GC (a) and GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs with undiluted MoS₂
 36 and variable CB[8] concentration for the synthesis of CB[8]-DNPs, 0.1 (b), 0.3 (c) and
 37 0.6 mM (d).

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47 **Figure S3.** Effect of the accumulation time in the CB[8]-MV²⁺ complex peak current with
48 the sensor GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs in 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 7 at 7.5 (a), 5.0 (b) and
49 2.5 μM (c) MV²⁺ concentrations. E_{ac} = - 0.9 V, amplitude = 60 mV, scan rate = 30 mV/s.

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62 **Figure S4.** DPV analysis by standard addition procedure of a river water sample fortified
 63 at $2.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M and diluted 1:10 in 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 7 with the platform
 64 GC/MoS₂/CB[8]-DNPs. Inset: Voltammograms of electrolyte (black line), 1:10 diluted
 65 fortified sample (red) and $1.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ to $5.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ MV²⁺ standard additions.

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